

Research Statement

From the inequitable global distribution of vaccines to the financial gulfs between billionaires and the workers who produce their wealth, evidence of social inequality is inescapable in the modern world. In a society increasingly interconnected through social media, the consequences of differential access to economic and cultural capital are well-documented. However, the pathways by which widespread social inequality first arose and the means by which inequity became naturalized and maintained are less well understood. My research takes a bioarchaeological approach to the emergence of social inequality by examining human skeletons from early complex societies.

From 2013–2016 I directed the Marroquíes Bioarchaeological Project with funding from the National Science Foundation, which focused on analyzing human remains from the site of Los Melgarejos, one of the first large-scale (113 ha) villages in Iberia. Over the course of over 270 salvage excavations at this site, archaeologists discovered abundant architectural evidence for managerial divisions of labor, including a series of deep concentric ditches and an adobe wall surrounding portions of the habitation area of the settlement. However, individuals were still buried collectively, in contrast to the individual depositions characteristic of the later and overtly hierarchical Bronze Age. My research brought together evidence from the human skeleton, grave goods, isotopic analyses of mobility and diet (C, N, O, Sr), and radiocarbon dating to investigate whether similar forms of mortuary treatment reflected or concealed significant differences in lived experience. My results showed that people at Marroquíes were treated similarly in both life and death, in contrast to other Iberian mega-villages which show evidence of wealth differentiation and mortuary populations that include up to 30% nonlocals. My work shows that there were multiple trajectories which led to the emergence of large villages, with some acting as centers of in-migration and increasing inequality and others emerging through local processes with little evidence for unequal access to resources, a finding with implications for understandings of the relationship between inequality and social complexity. This research formed the basis for my dissertation and has since been published in *Antiquity*, *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, *European Journal of Archaeology* and *American Anthropologist*.

Human skeletal remains from late prehistoric contexts are often fragmentary or commingled. As such, my methodological focus entails developing strategies for maximizing the biocultural information recoverable from incomplete skeletal remains in both prehistoric and contemporary contexts. My 2015 paper in the *Journal of Forensic Sciences* uses patterning in skeletal completion and element dispersal to assess the taphonomic factors that affected the preservation of skeletal remains in an arid desert environment. My 2016 article in the *Journal of Archaeological Sciences: Reports*, co-authored with former undergraduate mentee Katherine Kinkopf (Cal Poly Pomona), developed a logistic regression method to assess the likelihood that burials have been looted based on patterning in culturally significant anatomical regions. My most recent methodological paper in *International Journal of Osteoarchaeology* introduced a new strategy for assessing age from subadult tooth wear in archaeological assemblages containing large numbers of loose commingled teeth.

My upcoming research applies these quantitative and bioarchaeological methods to the larger anthropological problem of the emergence of inequality in early complex societies. First, I am

the project bioarchaeologist for the Copper Age site of Los Melgarejos, an enclosure site in Getafe, Spain containing at least fourteen distinct depositions of human remains. Los Melgarejos (4 ha) is a much smaller site than Marroquíes and thus provides a unique opportunity for increasing our understanding of the significant social transformations of the third millennium BC due to differences in scale, local ecology, and position in regional exchange networks. This aspect of my research takes a more geographically concentrated approach to the sweeping social changes of this period, focusing on how emerging inequalities were negotiated at the level of the local community. I am currently working on two manuscripts on these results—a larger bioarchaeological and isotopic analysis, and a more fine-grained osteobiographical investigation of a single mortuary deposit—for submission to the *Journal of Archaeological Science* and *Cambridge Archaeological Journal*, respectively.

Second, I have expanded my geographic focus to examine early complex societies in eastern Europe, developing a major mortuary and bioarchaeological field project—Mortuary Archaeology of the Râmeț Bronze Age Landscape (MARBAL)—in the Apuseni mountains of southwestern Transylvania, home to some of the richest reserves of copper and gold in the world. The first two seasons of MARBAL were funded by the European Commission through a Marie Skłodowska-Curie European Fellowship, during which I received training in conducting carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen isotopic analysis in the Dorothy Garrod Laboratory for Isotopic Analysis. This allowed me to analyze samples of human and faunal bone from Iberia and Transylvania in order to reconstruct aspects of past diet and mobility. This more recent training in archaeological science expanded my ability to understand lived experience in the past by adding biomolecular methods to my bioarchaeological toolkit. I am using the initial data collected in Transylvania to apply for a Cobb grant from the American Association of Biological Anthropologists, with plans to apply for NSF funding in coming years. The results of our team’s first seasons of analysis were published in two papers in a 2020 thematic issue of *Bioarchaeology International* (“Living and Dying in Mountain Landscapes”), for which I acted as co-editor.

I have also recently turned my attention to examining inequalities within the discipline of archaeology, with a focus on the intersection between knowledge production and academic publishing. My most recent paper in *American Antiquity* identifies and investigates prestige hierarchies in archaeological publishing, exploring how publishing decisions intersect with author identity, career considerations and the relationship between archaeology and the larger academy. As part of this new strand of my research, I am co-chairing an invited session at the 2022 Society for American Archaeology meetings on “Publishing Dynamics in Anthropology,” as well as developing an upper-level seminar on Bias in Archaeology (Spring 2022) with my current colleague Rowan Flad. Finally, I am developing an application for a Wenner-Gren symposium with my colleague Laura Heath-Stout titled “The Socio-Politics of Knowledge Production in Archaeology and Anthropology.”

Bioarchaeological research makes important contributions to the study of social inequality. My work weaves together bioarchaeological assessments of identity and lived experience, archaeological reconstructions of mortuary treatment, and isotopic analyses of ancient diet and mobility. As such, my research makes significant contributions to our understanding of the emergence of institutionalized inequality and how it is materialized and maintained in human bodies and communities in both past and present contexts.